

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Geospatial Entity Resolution Approach Integrating GeoHash Encoding and Heterogeneous Neighborhood Attention

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ABSTRACT

Geospatial entity resolution is crucial for geospatial data quality, aiming to identify records from different sources that refer to the same real-world entity. Traditional rule-based and similarity-driven methods often struggle with spatial heterogeneity, positioning errors, and textual inconsistency. Although deep learning approaches have shown promise, they still face challenges in capturing neighborhood context and jointly modeling semantic and spatial features. This paper presents a unified framework that integrates textual and spatial attributes for improved resolution accuracy. It first extracts semantic features using a fine-tuned pre-trained language model. Then, it applies GeoHash encoding to convert geographic coordinates into hierarchical strings, enhancing spatial representation. A heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism is introduced to dynamically aggregate semantic and spatial relationships between entities and their neighbors, adjusting discriminative weights in dense and sparse regions. Experiments on cross-source datasets (OSM, Yelp, Foursquare) from Singapore, Toronto, Pittsburgh, and Edinburgh demonstrate a 2.3% average F1-score improvement over the GeoER baseline. The proposed method performs well in both dense urban and sparse suburban contexts. Cross-city validation further confirms its generalization capability, supporting its effectiveness in diverse spatial environments.

KEYWORDS

Geospatial entity resolution; Pre-trained language model; Heterogeneous neighborhood attention; GeoHash encoding

1. Introduction

With the accelerating process of social informatization, applications such as navigation systems, digital maps, and smart cities have placed increasingly higher demands on the accurate resolution of geospatial data. Geospatial Entity Resolution (GER) plays a vital role in integrating geographic information from multiple data sources, thereby breaking the data silos created by the lack of interoperability between different map service providers. By parsing and fusing data, GER helps reduce errors and inconsistencies in geographic data, enhancing the overall accuracy of geospatial information. This technology is essential in various applications, including map services, navigation systems, and location-based search services (Gao & Widdows, 2024), and also provides critical decision support in fields such as urban planning, environmental monitoring, and disaster management (Hill, 2009).

In the study of geospatial entity resolution, the integration of geographic entities across heterogeneous data sources has attracted widespread attention. One of the earliest approaches, the schema element matching method proposed by Devogele, integrates spatial datasets by analyzing relationships between different data sources (Devogele, Parent, & Spaccapietra, 1998). Compared with ontology-based methods (Fonseca, Egenhofer, Agouris, & Câmara, 2002; J. Li, He, & Zhu, 2013; Zhu, Wang, & Li, 2009), its main advantage lies in its independence from large ontology libraries, allowing effective data matching and integration even in the absence of domain expert knowledge. Currently, feature-based approaches to geospatial entity matching can be broadly categorized into three main directions:

(1) **Geometry or Geospatial Attribute-Based Methods:**

These methods primarily rely on geographic coordinates to determine entity correspondences. For example, Safra (Safra, Kanza, Sagiv, & Doytsher, 2006) and Beeri (Beeri, Doytsher, Kanza, Safra, & Sagiv, 2005) employed location-based link analysis algorithms to identify matching entities across multiple data sources. Although geographic coordinates offer an intuitive basis for geospatial entity matching, relying solely on coordinate information often fails to guarantee high accuracy due to measurement errors, data protection strategies (e.g., coordinate obfuscation algorithms), and generalization in cartographic representations.

(2) **Descriptive and Non-Spatial Attribute-Based Methods:**

This category of methods leverages textual information such as place names and addresses for entity matching. For instance, Li et al. (X. Li, Morie, & Roth, 2005) utilized a global clustering algorithm and generative models to extract matches from ambiguous names, while Junchul (Kim, Vasardani, & Winter, 2017) combined string similarity with semantic analysis using a graph-based approach for toponym resolution. However, matching based on place names and addresses is often complicated by semantic ambiguities—such as a single name referring to multiple locations (e.g., “Hua Shan” may refer to different mountains in China)—which introduces additional challenges.

(3) **Hybrid Methods Combining Spatial and Non-Spatial Attributes:**

These methods aim to improve matching accuracy by fusing multidimensional features. For example, Liu (Liu, Chu, Hu, Feng, & Zhu, 2014) proposed a top-k spatial-textual similarity matching approach that jointly considers geographic locations and textual descriptions to identify the best matches. Scheffler (Scheffler, Schirru, & Lehmann, 2012) first applied a spatial filter and then matched points of interest (POIs) in social networks using name-based attributes. Safra (Safra, Kanza, Sagiv, Beeri, & and, 2010) extended traditional location-based methods by incorporating non-spatial attribute fusion algorithms. Moreover, McKenzie (McKenzie, Janowicz, & Adams, 2013) applied a binomial logistic regression model to assign matching weights and used a weighted multi-attribute model to enhance accuracy. Li (L. Li, Xing, Xia, & Huang, 2016) integrated heterogeneous attributes (e.g., spatial, name, category) and employed information entropy to assign attribute weights for more precise instance matching. Novack (Novack, Peters, & Zipf, 2018) proposed a graph-based matching strategy to resolve POI data conflicts, while Dsouza (Dsouza, Yu, Windoffer, & Demidova, 2023) adopted a cross-attention mechanism for aligning geospatial entities across different data sources. Additionally, Yang Bin et al. extracted Chinese semantic information from addresses using the ERNIE language model and combined

it with a knowledge-enhanced model to learn multi-level semantic features. A Conditional Random Field (CRF) was then used to calculate label combination probabilities, enabling boundary recognition and category mapping of address components.

In traditional geospatial entity resolution methods, spatial attributes are typically represented using geographic coordinates (i.e., longitude and latitude). However, this approach suffers from three major limitations. First, due to differences in measurement techniques, coordinate system shifts, and generalization errors in map rendering, cross-source coordinate misalignments are difficult to eliminate, which directly undermines matching accuracy. Second, absolute point-to-point positioning is inadequate for modeling the topological relationships between geographic entities (such as proximity and aggregation). This often leads to confusion when handling entities that are spatially close but semantically distinct—particularly in high-density areas. Third, brute-force matching based on coordinate similarity becomes computationally infeasible on large-scale datasets, as it incurs exponential growth in complexity, severely limiting the practicality of such algorithms.

To address the aforementioned challenges, this study proposes reconstructing the representation of geospatial entities using GeoHash-based spatial encoding. GeoHash maps two-dimensional geographic coordinates into multi-scale string encodings, which not only preserve spatial proximity (through prefix similarity) and regional aggregation (via hierarchical encoding granularity), but also significantly reduce the representational redundancy of high-dimensional coordinates. Compared to traditional methods, this discretized and structured spatial encoding offers twofold advantages. On one hand, its integration with textual features enables vector space alignment, allowing the model to jointly capture semantic associations and spatial distribution patterns. On the other hand, the encoded spatial features are more compatible with BERT-based pretrained language models, enabling the model to learn spatial distribution patterns embedded in the encoding sequences, thereby enhancing its ability to resolve complex geographic scenarios. Experiments demonstrate that this representation approach replaces exact coordinate comparison with error-tolerant encoded matching, which not only reduces computational complexity but also effectively mitigates cross-source alignment discrepancies. As a result, it provides a robust and efficient solution for geospatial entity resolution tasks.

Meanwhile, issues such as heterogeneity, missing values, and noisy data in geospatial entity resolution datasets remain key factors affecting matching accuracy. Traditional entity resolution methods rely on static similarity metrics, which often exhibit significant limitations in both sparse and dense urban scenarios. To address this, we propose a heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism that fully leverages the contextual information of surrounding entities. This approach enhances the model’s adaptability to complex geographic environments and significantly improves matching accuracy, especially under uneven spatial data distributions.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Chapter 1 introduces the research background, significance, current challenges in geospatial entity resolution, and outlines the main contributions. Chapter 2 reviews the related knowledge, including GeoHash encoding, the BERT pre-trained model, Transformer architecture, and graph attention networks. Chapter 3 presents the proposed method, covering the problem formulation, BERT-based entity matching, geospatial embeddings (distance and GeoHash), and the heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism. Chapter 4 details the experiments, including setup, datasets, baselines, and result analysis. Chapter 5 concludes with a

summary of the main work and contributions.

2. Related Knowledge

The complexity of geospatial entity resolution requires the integration of various technical approaches, with spatial representation and semantic understanding being two core challenges. To address these, this chapter provides a detailed overview of the background knowledge that supports our proposed method, including GeoHash encoding, the Transformer architecture, the BERT pre-trained language model, and Graph Attention Networks. These technologies form the theoretical foundation and offer critical support for the geospatial entity resolution approach presented in this study.

2.1. GeoHash Encoding

GeoHash is a spatial indexing method that encodes geographic coordinates into strings (Moussalli, Srivatsa, & Asaad, 2015). Proposed by Gustavo Niemeyer, it is widely used in tasks such as location retrieval and spatial aggregation. The core idea of GeoHash is to recursively divide the latitude and longitude space, mapping a two-dimensional geographic location into a one-dimensional string, thus enabling fast geolocation indexing and nearby region queries.

The GeoHash encoding process is based on the binary representation of latitude and longitude. It begins by bisecting the latitude range $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ and the longitude range $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$ at their midpoints. The target coordinates are recursively processed in this manner to generate an interleaved binary sequence. This binary sequence is then grouped into 5-bit segments and mapped to a Base32 encoding table, resulting in the final string representation. The longer the encoded string, the finer the spatial resolution and the higher the positional accuracy.

GeoHash exhibits spatial clustering properties: locations that are geographically close tend to share the same prefix in their encoded strings, making it suitable for efficient location identification and regional indexing. In geospatial entity resolution, GeoHash enables discretization of spatial data into encoded features, which facilitates integration with semantic features for cross-modal matching.

Figure 1. Step-by-Step Partitioning Process of GeoHash: The target point is first assigned to region k . The k region is then further partitioned, placing the point in sub-region e . This process continues iteratively until the point is finally located in the encoded region $ke2$.

Figure 1 illustrates the step-by-step spatial subdivision process of GeoHash encoding.

2.2. Transformer and BERT Pre-trained Language Model

The Transformer model was first proposed by Vaswani et al. in 2017 to address the challenges of long-range dependencies and limited parallelism in sequence modeling tasks. Unlike traditional recurrent neural networks, the Transformer discards the sequential recurrence structure and instead builds an encoder-decoder framework entirely based on the self-attention mechanism. Since entity resolution tasks only require feature extraction from input data, this section focuses on the design principles of the encoder module.

As shown in Figure 2, the Transformer encoder is composed of N identical layers stacked sequentially. Each layer contains two main sub-modules: a multi-head self-attention layer and a feed-forward neural network. The former captures multi-dimensional semantic dependencies within the input sequence by parallelizing multiple attention heads, while the latter, consisting of fully connected layers and residual connections, enhances the non-linear representation capacity of local features. Additionally, a positional encoding module is introduced to encode the order of the sequence, compensating for the self-attention mechanism’s lack of sensitivity to position information.

The core of the self-attention mechanism lies in its ability to dynamically model the interactions among elements within a sequence. Given an input sequence $A = [\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n] \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times n}$, where α_i denotes the initial vector representation of the i -th element, the query, key, and value matrices are generated through linear projections: $Q = AW^Q$, $K = AW^K$, and $V = AW^V$, where $W^Q, W^K, W^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_k}$ are learnable parameter matrices. The attention score function adopts the scaled dot-product form:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (1)$$

where d_k denotes the dimensionality of the key vectors, and the scaling factor $\sqrt{d_k}$ is introduced to mitigate the issue of large dot-product values, which can lead to gradient instability.

To enhance the model’s capability of disentangling semantic representations, the above process is executed in parallel h times (i.e., multihead attention), where each head employs independent projection matrices to generate $\{Q_i, K_i, V_i\}_i^h = 1$. The outputs of all heads are concatenated and linearly transformed to produce the final representation:

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \text{Concat}(\text{head}_1, \dots, \text{head}_h)W^O \quad (2)$$

where $W^O \in \mathbb{R}^{hd_v \times d}$ is the output projection matrix, and d_v denotes the dimensionality of the value vectors in each head.

Each encoder layer’s feed-forward neural network consists of two fully connected layers with a ReLU activation function: $FFN(x) = \text{ReLU}(xW_1 + b_1)W_2 + b_2$. Here, $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_{ff}}$, $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{ff} \times d}$, and d_{ff} represents the hidden layer’s dimensionality. To prevent network degradation, the output of each submodule is added to the input as a residual connection, followed by layer normalization: $x_{out} = \text{LayerNorm}(x + \text{Sublayer}(x))$. This design effectively mitigates the vanishing gradient problem in deep networks and enhances training stability. By fully parallelizing its structure and incorporating global

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the Transformer encoder structure

attention mechanisms, Transformer significantly improves the modeling efficiency of long sequences, laying the foundation for pre-trained models such as BERT and GPT. Its encoder module can capture semantic associations and spatial dependencies between entities through self-attention, thereby improving matching accuracy in entity resolution tasks.

Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT), proposed by Google in 2018, is a pre-trained language model based on a bidirectional Transformer encoder architecture. It aims to learn general-purpose language representations from large-scale corpora, significantly improving performance across various downstream natural language processing (NLP) tasks. The BERT model architecture consists of stacked Transformer encoders and is trained using two pre-training objectives: Masked Language Model (MLM) and Next Sentence Prediction (NSP). In the MLM task, a portion of the input tokens is randomly masked, and the model is required to predict the masked tokens based on the surrounding context, enabling bidirectional semantic learning. The NSP task determines whether two given sentences appear consecutively in the original text, enhancing the model’s ability to understand inter-sentence relationships.

At the input level, each token is represented as the sum of three vectors: a token embedding, a positional embedding, and a segment embedding. This combined representation is projected into the model’s hidden space. BERT captures deep semantic features through multiple layers of Transformer encoders, with each output vector at a given position representing the contextual semantics of the corresponding token. With shared training across all tokens, the model can be effectively fine-tuned for downstream tasks such as entity recognition, question answering, and text matching. By leveraging large-scale unsupervised pre-training and task-specific fine-tuning with limited annotated data, BERT alleviates the issue of data scarcity in supervised learning. Its strong capability for deep semantic modeling and generalizable representations

provides a robust semantic foundation for entity resolution tasks.

2.3. Graph Neural Networks and Graph Attention Networks

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)(Wu et al., 2021) are a class of deep learning models specifically designed to process data represented in the form of graphs or networks. A graph is a powerful data structure used to encode relationships between entities, and GNNs are capable of leveraging these relationships to extract meaningful features for tasks such as node classification, link prediction, and graph-level inference. The goal of GNNs is to learn embedding representations that capture both the structural information of the graph and the attributes of individual nodes.

GNNs achieve this by propagating messages between nodes in the graph, aggregating information from neighboring nodes, and updating each node’s representation accordingly. These message-passing and update steps are repeated across multiple layers, enabling the model to capture increasingly complex relationships among nodes. The final node embeddings can then be utilized for various downstream tasks.

In a basic GNN, the vector representation of a node A , denoted as h_A , with its neighboring node set N_A , is computed as:

$$h_A = \sum_{i \in N_A} x_i W^T \tag{3}$$

where W is the learnable weight matrix of the neural network, and x_i denotes the input feature vector of each neighbor of node A . The matrix form of this operation can be expressed as:

$$H = \bar{A}XW^T \tag{4}$$

where H is the matrix of node embeddings, X is the node feature matrix, and $\bar{A} = A+I$ is the adjacency matrix of the input graph with added self-loops, where I is the identity matrix.

Graph Attention Networks (GATs) (Veličković et al., 2018)adopt the attention mechanism to assign learnable scaling factors when aggregating information from neighboring nodes. This attention-based approach enables GATs to allocate larger weights to more important neighbors, allowing for finer-grained control over the information flow within complex graph structures. As a result, GATs are particularly well-suited for handling heterogeneous or unstructured data. In contrast, when the graph structure is well-defined and each node contributes equally, Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs) are often more efficient.

To achieve this, the graph attention layer in a GAT performs several operations on the input graph data. Initially, each node undergoes a shared linear transformation via a learnable weight matrix W , laying the foundation for subsequent analysis and processing. The result of the graph attention operation is illustrated in Figure 3.

Following the initial linear transformation, the model proceeds to compute attention coefficients. These coefficients represent unnormalized attention weights calculated pairwise between a node and each of its neighbors. At this stage, the transformed feature vectors of two neighboring nodes are concatenated to form a joint representation.

Figure 3. Illustration of a Graph Attention Network

This concatenated vector is then subjected to a dot product with a learnable weight vector, effectively integrating node features into the attention mechanism.

To introduce non-linearity into the model, the result of the dot product operation is passed through a LeakyReLU activation function. The next step is to normalize the attention coefficients to ensure consistency across all nodes. This is achieved using the softmax function, which ensures that the coefficients are comparable and appropriately scaled.

During the aggregation phase, the model combines the embedding vectors from neighboring nodes according to the computed attention weights. However, a key concern in Graph Attention Networks (GATs) is the potential instability of self-attention. To mitigate this issue, the concept of multi-head attention is adopted. This approach involves creating multiple parallel attention mechanisms—referred to as “heads”—each with its own set of learnable parameters. These heads operate concurrently to enhance the model’s capacity and training stability.

Each attention head computes its own output, and these outputs are then integrated to form the final representation. Typically, in intermediate layers, the outputs from all heads are concatenated, whereas in the final layer, an average is taken to combine the information from multiple perspectives. In GATs, attention weights are implicitly determined by comparing node features pairwise, as illustrated in the figure.

The mathematical formulation for computing the representation of node i is as follows:

$$h_i = \sum_{j \in N_i} a_{ij} W x_j \quad (5)$$

where a_{ij} denotes the attention weight dynamically computed by the network, and W is the shared linear transformation matrix.

3. Method

In previous methods for geographic entity resolution and matching, language models were primarily used to capture the similarity of textual attributes, while numerical embeddings were employed to describe the spatial proximity between two geographic points of interest (POIs) to be matched. These two components were then combined to determine whether they constitute a match.

To address the task of geospatial entity resolution, we propose a matching model named Hierarchical Matching Network for Joint Framework Entity Resolution (**HMN-JFER**), which integrates both textual and spatial information. The core idea is to comprehensively capture the semantic and spatial characteristics of entities by combining pretrained language models with spatial embedding techniques, thereby improving the matching accuracy. The overall model architecture is illustrated in Figure 4. The model consists of three major components:

- (1) **Semantic Encoding Module.** A pretrained language model BERT, is fine-tuned to adapt to the geospatial entity resolution task, producing textual embedding vectors for each entity.
- (2) **Spatial Embedding Module.** This module is designed with two alternative strategies. One approach calculates the distance between entities based on latitude and longitude and encodes it numerically. The other approach transforms the geographic coordinates into GeoHash encodings, which are then input into the pretrained language model along with textual attributes to jointly capture spatial relationships between entities.
- (3) **Neighborhood Attention Module.** This module dynamically aggregates the semantic and spatial contexts of the central entity and its neighboring entities to build a context-aware representation, thereby enhancing the model’s ability to handle complex geographic scenarios.

Finally, the neighborhood-aware context representation is concatenated with other feature vectors to form a unified representation, which is passed into a classification layer specifically optimized for geospatial entity resolution to determine whether a given entity pair matches.

3.1. Problem Definition

The geospatial entity resolution problem considered in this work is defined as follows: given two geospatial databases, D_1 and D_2 , containing $|D_1|$ and $|D_2|$ records respectively, the goal is to identify all pairs of entities from D_1 and D_2 that refer to the same real-world entity. Such pairs are referred to as matching entities.

A geospatial entity e_i is represented by a set of textual attributes $\{name_i, address_i, zipcode_i\}$ and a spatial location $\{latitude_i, longitude_i\}$.

Blocking Strategy. In real-world scenarios, performing $|D_1| \times |D_2|$ pairwise comparisons across all entities from D_1 and D_2 is computationally infeasible. Therefore, the goal of the blocking phase is to retrieve a candidate set C consisting of potentially matching entity pairs. This reduces the number of comparisons needed, allowing fine-grained matching functions to be applied only to candidate pairs, thus accelerating the entire resolution process.

In this study, we adopt an effective blocking strategy for geospatial data, which is based on both textual similarity and spatial proximity. Specifically, we use the

Figure 4. Geospatial entity resolution framework with neighborhood attention mechanism

Levenshtein edit distance to measure the name similarity. For each entity pair $(e_i, e_j) \in D_1 \times D_2$, it is considered a matching candidate if it satisfies the following condition:

$$\text{Levenshtein}(\text{name}_i, \text{name}_j) \geq 0.6 \wedge \text{dist}(e_i, e_j) \leq 2000 \quad (6)$$

We select a relatively high distance threshold to maximize the recall.

3.2. Entity Matching Model Based on BERT

Previous learning-based entity matching models typically relied on word embeddings and customized recurrent neural network (RNN) architectures to train the matching model. However, recent approaches have achieved competitive performance by fine-tuning pre-trained language models within simpler architectures.

In this work, we adopt a 12-layer BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) model and fine-tune it for the entity matching task. Each pair of data entries in the original dataset is serialized and then fed into the language model as input. The output is a binary classification decision indicating whether the entity pair is a match or not.

The pre-trained language model can be fine-tuned using task-specific training data to better perform the target task. In our case, we fine-tune the pre-trained language model on a labeled dataset specifically designed for the entity matching task. This dataset contains both positive (matching) and negative (non-matching) pairs of entity entries. The fine-tuning process involves the following steps:

- (1) **Add task-specific layers:** A task-specific classification layer is added on top of the final layer of the language model. For entity matching, we use a simple fully connected layer followed by a softmax output layer to perform binary

classification.

- (2) **Train the modified network:** The modified model is trained on the training dataset until convergence. The result is a fine-tuned model specifically adapted for the entity matching task.

Since the language model takes tokenized text sequences as input, a key challenge is how to convert candidate entity pairs into token sequences that can be meaningfully processed by the pre-trained language model. The serialization process of each data entry is as follows: for a data entry $e = \{(attr_i, val_i)\}_{1 \leq i \leq k}$,

$$serialize(e) = [COL] attr_1 [VAL] val_1 \dots [COL] attr_k [VAL] val_k \quad (7)$$

where [COL] and [VAL] are special tokens indicating the start of an attribute name and its corresponding value, respectively.

The serialization of a candidate pair (e, e') is as follows:

$$serialize(e, e') = [CLS] serialize(e) [SEP] serialize(e') [SEP] \quad (8)$$

where [SEP] is a special separator token between the two entries, and [CLS] is a classification token required by BERT to encode the input sequence pair into a 768-dimensional vector, which is subsequently fed into a fully connected layer for classification.

Table 1. Fine-tuning Process of the BERT-based Entity Matching Model

Fine-tuning Steps
Input: Candidate entity pair dataset X , ground-truth labels Y
Output: Model prediction results R
Step 1: Initialize the language model by loading the pre-trained BERT and adding a classification layer. Prepare the dataset.
Step 2: For each text pair (text1, text2):
a) Construct the input sequence with special tokens: [CLS] text1 [SEP] text2 [SEP]
b) Use a tokenizer to convert the text into a sequence of token IDs
c) Generate the attention mask to distinguish real tokens from padding
d) Truncate or pad the sequence to the maximum length
Step 3: Training loop
a) Iterate over all samples in X and obtain predictions R using the BERT model
b) Compute the loss between R and Y using a loss function and update the model via backpropagation
Step 4: Complete all training epochs
Step 5: Validate the fine-tuned model on the validation set and save the best-performing parameters

The pseudocode of the fine-tuning process for the BERT-based entity matching model is shown in Table 1.

Traditional pre-trained language models are primarily optimized for textual data, and their training processes typically do not involve the handling of geographic information. These models focus mainly on vocabulary, grammar, and semantic patterns within the text, learning contextualized word embeddings from large-scale textual corpora. As a result, when raw latitude and longitude data are directly input into such models, they struggle to comprehend the spatial significance conveyed by these numerical values.

To address this limitation, it is essential to transform geographic coordinates into representations that the language model can better understand and utilize. By converting latitude and longitude data into a more suitable format, the model can more effectively capture the spatial relationships between geographic entities, thereby improving the accuracy of geospatial entity resolution.

In the following sections, we provide a detailed description of the basic method of distance embedding and propose an enhanced approach using GeoHash encoding. A comparison between these two methods is also presented to evaluate their respective advantages and limitations.

3.3. Geospatial Information Embedding

3.3.1. Distance-Based Embedding

An intuitive approach is to add a separate module within the network architecture dedicated to distance computation and embedding. This design choice equips the model with the ability to explicitly incorporate spatial relationships. The Haversine formula is used to compute the distance between two candidate entities i and j :

$$d_{ij} = \text{Haversine}(\phi_i, \phi_j, \lambda_i, \lambda_j, r) \quad (9)$$

$$S = 2 \arcsin \sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{a}{2} + \cos(\text{Lat1}) \times \cos(\text{Lat2}) \times \sin^2 \frac{b}{2}} \times r \quad (10)$$

where (ϕ_i, λ_i) represents the latitude and longitude of entity i , and r is the radius of the Earth. Here, $a = \text{Lat1} - \text{Lat2}$, and $b = \text{Lng1} - \text{Lng2}$. The computed distance is then continuously scaled to the range $[-1, 1]$ and embedded into a fixed-dimensional array of size d_{dist} as follows:

$$\text{EMB}(d_{ij}) = \alpha_{dist}^T \cdot \left(\frac{2 \cdot d_{ij}}{\text{maxdist} - 1} + \beta_{dist} \right) \quad (11)$$

Here, $\alpha_{dist} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{dist}}$ and $\beta_{dist} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{dist}}$ are trainable parameters, and maxdist refers to the maximum distance observed among the candidate entity pairs selected during the blocking phase.

By embedding the distance information into a fixed-size vector, this approach effectively manages numerical range, scale variation, and potential non-linear relationships, thereby enhancing model performance and generalization. The distance embedding is concatenated with the output of the language model and fed into the final classifier to

produce the prediction. The overall structure is illustrated in Figure 5. The pseudocode for the distance embedding process is shown in Table 2.

Figure 5. The architecture of the proposed geospatial entity resolution model. The left part illustrates the BERT-based entity resolution module, where two entities are tokenized and encoded using a Transformer encoder. The contextual representation of the sequence is obtained from the [CLS] token. The right part shows the distance embedding module, where geospatial coordinates (latitude and longitude) are processed through distance calculation, normalization, and numerical embedding. The outputs from both modules are fused and fed into a classifier to determine whether the entity pair is a match or mismatch.

3.3.2. Embedding Based on GeoHash Encoding

The primary advantage of distance embedding lies in its ability to capture geographical distance relationships. However, it suffers from several limitations. First, distance embedding often entails high computational complexity, especially when processing large-scale data, leading to increased computation and storage costs. Second, it is difficult for distance embedding to directly express spatial proximity between geographic entities, often requiring additional computation and storage to maintain spatial relationships. Finally, distance embedding usually generates fixed-dimensional vectors, which lack the benefit of data compression and are therefore inefficient for storage and transmission in large-scale scenarios. These drawbacks pose challenges for geographic entity resolution tasks.

To address these issues, this paper proposes the use of GeoHash encoding for latitude and longitude data. GeoHash is a hierarchical spatial data structure that organizes data by dividing the space into different grids. It supports arbitrary encoding precision and improves efficiency by reducing the number of bits used for feature representation, thus shortening the final encoding length. However, reducing the number of bits leads to a gradual loss of spatial precision. Typically, geographically adjacent locations share similar prefixes in their GeoHash codes; the more characters they share in the prefix, the closer the locations are to each other.

When performing GeoHash encoding for geographic coordinates, the longitude and latitude must first be converted into their respective binary representations. The specific steps are as follows:

Table 2. Distance Embedding Process

Distance Embedding
Input: Latitude and longitude coordinates of entity pairs to be matched: $lat_1, long_1, lat_2, long_2$
Output: Distance embedding Y
1. Initialize configuration parameters: hidden size and embedding dimension, and prepare data.
2. Process coordinate data for each coordinate pair $(lat_1, lon_1, lat_2, lon_2)$: a) Use the Haversine formula to compute the distance $dist$ between the two geographic coordinates. b) Normalize the distance into the range $[-1, 1]$. c) Convert the normalized distance to a tensor and move it to the specified device. d) Use an embedding layer to map the distance to an embedding vector.
3. Return the distance embedding result Y .

- (1) **Binary encoding:** Compute the binary encoding for both longitude and latitude. This typically involves mapping the coordinate values into a predefined range and converting them into binary form.
- (2) **Interleaving:** According to the rule “even bits for longitude, odd bits for latitude starting from index 0,” interleave the bits of longitude and latitude to form a single binary sequence. This step alternately integrates the longitude and latitude information.
- (3) **Grouping and base32 conversion:** Divide the resulting binary sequence into groups of five bits. For each group, compute its decimal value and use it as an index to retrieve the corresponding character from the base32 encoding table.
- (4) **Concatenation:** Concatenate all the base32 characters to obtain the final Geo-Hash value.

Using the coordinate point (104.06638546, 30.6599157) as an example, the process for generating binary encoding for longitude or latitude includes the following steps:

- (1) **Define the initial range:** The range for longitude is set to $[-180^\circ, +180^\circ]$, and for latitude to $[-90^\circ, +90^\circ]$.
- (2) **Interval halving:** Divide the current interval in half. Depending on whether the coordinate lies in the left or right half, assign a binary digit. Use 0 for the left half and 1 for the right half.
- (3) **Recursive subdivision:** Continue halving the subinterval where the coordinate lies, assigning binary digits in the same manner as above.
- (4) **Repeat until desired precision:** Repeat the process until the binary sequence reaches the target encoding length. The iteration details are shown in Table 3.

Through the above calculation, the 15-bit binary encoding for the latitude value 30.6599157 is: 101010111001101. Similarly, the 15-bit binary encoding for the longitude value 104.0638546 is 110010100000000.

The obtained binary representations of the longitude and latitude are then interleaved starting from the 0-th bit—placing the longitude bits in even positions and the

Table 3. Iteration Process for Binary Encoding of Latitude

Iteration	Left Bound	Midpoint	Right Bound	Result (0/1)
1	0.000000	0.000000	90.000000	1
2	0.000000	45.000000	90.000000	0
3	0.000000	22.500000	45.000000	1
4	22.500000	33.750000	45.000000	0
5	22.500000	28.125000	33.750000	1
6	28.125000	30.937500	33.750000	0
7	28.125000	29.531250	30.937500	1
8	29.531250	30.234375	30.937500	1
9	30.234375	30.585938	30.937500	1
10	30.585938	30.761719	30.937500	0
11	30.585938	30.673828	30.761719	0
12	30.585938	30.629883	30.673828	1
13	30.629883	30.651855	30.673828	1
14	30.651855	30.662842	30.673828	0
15	30.651855	30.657349	30.662842	1

latitude bits in odd positions—resulting in a combined binary sequence. This process is illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Binary Encoding of Latitude and Longitude

To compress the length of the encoding, GeoHash employs a custom Base32 encoding scheme to convert the binary sequence into a more compact and human-readable format. The Base32 encoding used in GeoHash consists of digits and letters, excluding the characters *a*, *i*, *l*, and *o* to avoid visual ambiguity. The mapping table of the Base32 encoding used in GeoHash is shown in Figure 7.

Referring to the encoding table, the interleaved binary sequence is divided into groups of five bits, and each group is converted into its corresponding decimal value. These values are then mapped to their respective characters in the Base32 table, yielding the final GeoHash encoding `wm6n2j`, as illustrated in Figure 8.

The length of the GeoHash encoding determines the spatial resolution. The desired precision is determined by the application requirements. For high-precision applications, a longer GeoHash code should be used. Since pre-trained language models are well-suited for handling textual data, the GeoHash code can be combined with textual attributes of entities (such as names or addresses) and fed into the model. This enables the fusion of semantic and spatial information, allowing the model to capture not only the semantic characteristics of entities but also their spatial features, thereby

Decimal Number	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Base 32	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	b	c	d	e	f	g
Decimal Number	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31
Base 32	h	j	k	m	n	p	q	r	s	t	u	v	w	x	y	z

Figure 7. GeoHash Base32 Encoding Table

Figure 8. Computation of the GeoHash Encoding

enhancing the performance of geographic entity matching and resolution.

3.4. Neighborhood Attention Mechanism

Traditional geographic entity resolution methods often suffer from limitations such as static similarity measurements, rigid rule-based strategies, susceptibility to geolocation errors, and challenges arising from missing or heterogeneous textual attributes. Additionally, the disconnection between local and global contextual information, as well as the one-dimensional nature of static similarity metrics, reveals the shortcomings of conventional approaches in semantic-spatial coupling, adaptability to dynamic environments, and the fusion of multi-source information.

To address these issues, we introduce a neighborhood attention mechanism. By dynamically integrating graph attention networks with spatial bias, this mechanism enables the joint encoding of semantic similarity and spatial proximity. It also supports adaptive weighting based on neighborhood density and facilitates the complementary enhancement of multi-source contextual information, offering a novel solution for entity matching in complex geographic scenarios.

3.4.1. Constructing Heterogeneous Neighborhoods

In geographic entity resolution tasks, a neighborhood refers to a set of entities that are spatially adjacent to the target entity. These neighboring entities are not only geographically close but may also be semantically related to the target. Spatial proximity

and name similarity constitute the basis of these inter-entity relationships. When the association between entities exceeds a certain threshold, we define the neighborhood as a heterogeneous neighborhood. For instance, in a commercial area, the neighborhood of a target entity such as a coffee shop may include nearby coffee shops, restaurants, and retail stores. The attributes and spatial relationships of these nearby entities provide valuable contextual information that helps the model better understand the characteristics and background of the target entity. The process of neighborhood construction involves the following three sub-steps: spatial proximity filtering, name-based semantic similarity filtering, and removal of redundant candidate entity pairs.

Spatial proximity filtering preliminarily identifies candidate neighbors based on the geographical distance between entities. First, according to the characteristics of geospatial data, a maximum neighborhood radius δ_{\max} is defined, which should be adjusted based on urban density. For example, in densely populated urban areas (such as Orchard Road in Singapore), δ_{\max} can be set to 200 meters; whereas in suburban areas where entities are more sparsely distributed, it can be increased to 500 meters. This dynamic adjustment strategy allows the filtering process to adapt to varying geographic environments, enhancing both the flexibility and accuracy of neighbor selection. Once the maximum neighborhood radius is determined, the Haversine formula is employed to calculate the spherical distance between entities. Only entity pairs satisfying $d_{ij} \leq \delta_{\max}$ are retained as candidate neighbors. This filtering step ensures that the neighboring entities are spatially proximate, laying a foundation for subsequent semantic similarity analysis.

The candidate neighbors obtained solely through spatial proximity filtering may include many entities that are semantically irrelevant to the target entity. Therefore, a further refinement step is conducted using **name-based semantic similarity filtering**. The core of this step involves encoding entity names into semantic representations using a pre-trained language model and evaluating the semantic relevance between entity names via cosine similarity. First, the entity names are preprocessed by converting all characters to lowercase and removing special symbols, in order to reduce noise that may interfere with semantic encoding. Then, the preprocessed names are fed into a pre-trained BERT-base model to obtain semantic representations. Specifically, the hidden state corresponding to the [CLS] token is extracted as the semantic vector representation h_{name} of the entity name. Leveraging the powerful contextual modeling capabilities of BERT, this process captures rich semantic features of entity names in diverse contexts, thus providing high-quality vector embeddings for similarity computation. Subsequently, cosine similarity is used to compute the semantic similarity between entity names. The formula is defined as:

$$\text{sim}(i, j) = \frac{h_{\text{name}_i} \cdot h_{\text{name}_j}}{|h_{\text{name}_i}| \cdot |h_{\text{name}_j}|} \quad (12)$$

A similarity threshold τ is set, and only entities satisfying $\text{sim}(i, j) \geq \tau$ are retained as final neighboring entities. This filtering step not only removes entities that are semantically unrelated to the target entity but also preserves those with similar semantic characteristics, thereby providing rich semantic information for constructing context-aware representations. If two entities e_1 and e_2 from a candidate matching pair appear in each other’s neighbor lists simultaneously, it may introduce incorrect contextual signals during model training, thus adversely affecting the accuracy of entity resolution. Therefore, such candidate matching pairs (e_1, e_2) are removed from the final neighborhood. The process of constructing a heterogeneous neighborhood is

illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Heterogeneous neighborhood construction

3.4.2. Neighborhood Attention

Based on Graph Attention Networks (GAT), this paper proposes a dynamic neighborhood information aggregation mechanism to enhance the accuracy of geographic entity resolution. This mechanism learns attention weights between nodes to dynamically aggregate information from neighboring nodes, thereby generating richer context-aware representations. The detailed process is as follows:

1. **Linear Transformation:** In the graph attention mechanism, each node’s BERT-based representation h_i is first linearly projected into a lower-dimensional space. This step reduces computational complexity and enhances the model’s expressive capability. The transformation is defined as:

$$z_i = W \cdot h_i \quad (13)$$

where W is a learnable weight matrix initialized using He normal initialization. The He initialization strategy effectively mitigates the vanishing gradient problem and ensures stable convergence in the early stages of training. By projecting high-dimensional BERT representations into a more compact space, the model not only improves computational efficiency but also provides more concise feature embeddings for the subsequent attention score calculation.

2. **Attention Score Computation:** To compute attention scores, this study introduces a joint weighting mechanism that integrates both semantic similarity and spatial proximity, thereby capturing the combined influence of semantic relations and geographic distance between nodes. The attention score is defined as:

$$e_{ij} = \text{LeakyReLU} \left(a^T (z_i \| z_j + \phi \cdot \frac{1}{d_{ij} + \epsilon}) \right) \quad (14)$$

Here, a is the attention parameter vector, initialized with a zero-mean Gaussian distribution, and is used to learn semantic correlations between node pairs. The scalar ϕ is a learnable parameter that controls the strength of the distance bias. By adjusting ϕ , the model can adaptively balance the effects of semantic similarity and spatial distance. The constant ϵ is used to avoid division-by-zero errors and ensures numerical stability.

In this formulation, the low-dimensional embedding z_i of each point of interest incorporates its name $name_i$, relative orientation dir_i , and street name similarity $street_i$. The low-dimensional embeddings z_i and z_j of nodes i and j are concatenated to form a joint feature vector. This vector is then linearly transformed by the attention vector a and passed through a LeakyReLU activation function to introduce non-linearity.

To explicitly incorporate spatial proximity, a distance bias term $\phi \cdot \frac{1}{d_{ij} + \epsilon}$ is added, where d_{ij} denotes the geographical distance between nodes i and j . This formulation allows the model to jointly encode name semantic similarity, relative orientation, street name similarity, and spatial proximity into the attention score, thereby mitigating the bias caused by reliance on a single dimension.

The overall computation process is illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Attention score computation in heterogeneous neighborhood

After computing the attention scores, the Softmax function is applied to normalize these scores, ensuring that the attention weights for each node sum to 1. The normalization is defined as follows:

$$a_{ij} = \frac{\exp(e_{ij})}{\sum_{k \in N(i)} \exp(e_{ik})} \quad (15)$$

where $N(i)$ denotes the set of neighboring nodes of node i . The normalized attention weight a_{ij} represents the importance of node j to node i . Subsequently, the representation of node i is generated by aggregating the representations of its neighbors in a weighted manner:

$$n_i = \text{ReLU} \left(\sum_{j \in N(i)} a_{ij} \cdot z_j \right) \quad (16)$$

If entity i has no neighbors satisfying the given conditions, its representation n_i is set to a zero vector. This approach effectively handles sparse neighborhoods, ensuring the robustness of the model across different scenarios. To address sparsity, the neighborhood attention mechanism adopts multi-neighbor aggregation. Even when there is a localization error for the target entity, the model can still make accurate matching decisions by aggregating both semantic and spatial information from surrounding neighbors (such as the types and density of nearby entities).

For example, even if the coordinates of a shopping mall entrance are slightly shifted, the spatial distribution of nearby entities (e.g., parking lots or stores) can still provide useful cues for matching. The model also dynamically adjusts the neighborhood range based on regional density (e.g., extending to 500 meters in suburban areas), expanding the search radius to include potential matches and avoid missing candidates due to a single localization error. Additionally, a distance bias term is incorporated into the attention scores to reduce the impact of small localization errors. Even when the actual distance slightly exceeds a threshold due to such errors, the model can still make correct matching decisions by leveraging contextual information from the neighborhood.

In dense scenarios, the neighborhood attention mechanism incorporates contextual information to mitigate matching errors. When multiple entities with the same name exist near the target entity, the model lowers the matching weight for the current candidate, treating it as an independent branch rather than a correct match. For instance, through attention weight adjustment, the model can recognize that several entities named “Starbucks” already exist nearby and thus avoid incorrect matches. Furthermore, the attention scores jointly encode both semantic similarity of names and spatial proximity, preventing the model from relying solely on a single dimension. Even if two entities named “Starbucks” are semantically similar and geographically close, the presence of other entities with the same name in the vicinity will reduce the matching probability through contextual neighborhood cues. Finally, a learnable parameter (e.g., ϕ) is introduced to dynamically balance the influence of semantic similarity and spatial distance. In dense areas, the model tends to rely more on the semantic similarity of neighborhood features rather than absolute distances.

3.5. Fusion and Output

In the task of geospatial entity resolution, fusing neighborhood contextual representations with other features is a crucial step in generating the final matching probability. By integrating multiple types of features, the model can effectively leverage textual attributes, spatial distances, and neighborhood context information to enhance matching accuracy. The fusion process is defined as follows:

$$f = h_i \parallel \text{Emb}(d_{ij}) \parallel n_i \quad (17)$$

Here, h_i represents the encoded textual attributes, $\text{Emb}(d_{ij})$ denotes the distance embedding. In this work, we apply GeoHash encoding to incorporate spatial distance information, which is then fused with textual features. n_i refers to the neighborhood contextual representation. The concatenated feature vector f_i thus contains textual, spatial, and contextual information, providing a rich representation for the subsequent classification task.

To generate the final matching probability from the concatenated feature vector, a simple classifier is designed. The classifier consists of a fully connected layer followed by an output layer. The concatenated vector f_i is first projected to a 512-dimensional

space to reduce computational complexity and improve model expressiveness. The transformation is defined as:

$$g_i = \text{ReLU}(W_f \cdot f_i + b_f) \quad (18)$$

Here, W_f and b_f are learnable parameters, and ReLU is the activation function used to introduce non-linearity. The fully connected layer performs dimensionality reduction to extract key information from the feature vector, providing a more compact representation for the subsequent output layer. Finally, the matching probability p is generated using a Sigmoid function, as defined below:

$$p = \text{Sigmoid}(W_o \cdot g_i + b_o) \quad (19)$$

In this equation, W_o and b_o are learnable parameters, and the Sigmoid function maps the output value to the range $[0, 1]$. The output of the Sigmoid function represents the matching probability of the entity pair, where a value closer to 1 indicates a higher likelihood of a correct match.

4. Experimental Analysis

In this chapter, we conduct extensive experiments on datasets from four cities within three real-world location-based services. The F1-score is adopted as the evaluation metric to assess model performance. The experimental results are reported and compared with four state-of-the-art models, including our proposed HMN-JFER.

Section 4.1 introduces the experimental setup, including the environment configuration, model parameter settings, and evaluation metrics. Section 4.2 describes the datasets and baseline methods. Section 4.3 presents the experiments and comparative analysis, which include overall experimental results, ablation studies, and an analysis of the neighborhood attention mechanism under specific scenarios.

4.1. Experimental Setup

All experiments in this study were conducted on a computer running the Windows operating system, with the following hardware specifications: CPU: AMD Ryzen 7 7745HX with Radeon Graphics; Memory: 32GB; GPU: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4070 (8GB). The open-source deep learning framework used is PyTorch, the code editor is Visual Studio Code, and the Python interpreter version is 3.7.12.

In the experiments, the hidden size of BERT is set to 768, while both the distance embedding and the neighborhood embedding are set to 256 dimensions. During training, the model is optimized using the Adam optimizer, with a learning rate of $3e-5$ and a dropout rate of 0.1. A linear decay learning rate schedule is applied, and the batch size is set to 32. For each experiment, the model is trained for 20 epochs depending on the size of the dataset.

This study adopts the F1-score as the evaluation metric for each class, and uses Overall Accuracy (OA) as the overall performance indicator of the model. Here, TP (True Positives) refers to the number of positive samples that are correctly predicted as positive; TN (True Negatives) refers to the number of negative samples correctly predicted as negative; FP (False Positives) represents the number of negative samples

incorrectly predicted as positive; and FN (False Negatives) indicates the number of positive samples incorrectly predicted as negative.

Accuracy reflects the proportion of correctly predicted samples among all samples, and is calculated as follows:

$$OA = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (20)$$

Precision measures the proportion of correctly predicted positive samples among all samples predicted as positive, and is defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (21)$$

Recall measures the proportion of actual positive samples that are correctly predicted, and is given by:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (22)$$

F1-score represents the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and is calculated as:

$$F1 = \frac{2 \cdot Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (23)$$

4.2. Dataset

The experimental data used in this study are collected from three real-world location-based services: OpenStreetMap (OSM), Foursquare (FSQ), and Yelp. OpenStreetMap is a collaborative platform for building a free geographic database of the world. Users can add points of interest (POIs), which are represented as geographic coordinates. We adopted the same attribute schema as used in the first two data sources. Yelp is a crowdsourced review platform that provides full names, addresses, postal codes, and coordinate information for each POI. Foursquare is a location-based social network where users check in at places they visit to earn points and rewards. The dataset offers anonymized user check-in data.

An overview of the number of POIs in each dataset is shown in Table 4, and the percentage of POIs with non-empty addresses is shown in Table 5.

Table 4. Statistics of OSM, FSQ, and Yelp Datasets

City	OSM	FSQ	Yelp
Singapore	23,985	31,936	13,699
Edinburgh	11,389	7,549	3,868
Toronto	38,286	18,851	17,204
Pittsburgh	9,387	11,579	6,356

For each data source, the dataset includes four cities: Singapore, Edinburgh, Toronto, and Pittsburgh. Each entity contains essential information such as name,

postal code, phone number, and geographic coordinates. The candidate set C is obtained using the blocking method described in Chapter 3. For each entity pair in C , if the two entities refer to the same real-world object, it is labeled as a match; otherwise, it is labeled as a non-match.

After applying the blocking strategy, we obtained the statistics for each dataset. The percentage of POIs with non-empty addresses is shown in Table 5. After annotation, two datasets were generated: OSM-FSQ and OSM-Yelp, covering all four cities with a total of 194,090 entity pairs. Detailed statistics are provided in Table 6.

Table 5. Percentage of POIs with Non-empty Addresses in OSM, FSQ, and Yelp

City	OSM	FSQ	Yelp
Singapore	40%	54%	99%
Edinburgh	57%	61%	99%
Toronto	33%	72%	98%
Pittsburgh	28%	58%	97%

Table 6. Statistics of OSM-FSQ and OSM-Yelp Datasets

Dataset	City	Size	Positive Pairs (%)	Non-empty Address
OSM-FSQ	Singapore	19,243	2,116 (11.0%)	25.5%
	Edinburgh	17,386	3,350 (19.3%)	45.5%
	Toronto	17,858	3,862 (21.6%)	32.0%
	Pittsburgh	5,001	1,454 (29.6%)	25.5%
OSM-Yelp	Singapore	21,588	2,941 (13.6%)	51.6%
	Edinburgh	18,733	2,310 (12.3%)	74.0%
	Toronto	27,969	5,429 (19.4%)	39.9%
	Pittsburgh	5,116	1,622 (31.7%)	38.8%

4.3. Overview of Comparative Methods

DeepMatcher (Xie, Dai, Wang, Li, & Zhao, 2023) is one of the best-performing entity resolution solutions currently available. It aggregates the attributes of entities using an RNN, integrating different attribute information to form a comprehensive entity representation. For instance, for an entity that contains attributes such as name, address, and phone number, the RNN sequentially inputs these attribute values into the network and gradually aggregates them into a vector that represents the entire entity. This method uses the RNN to compare the attribute values of different entities. By comparing the attribute value sequences of two entities, it calculates their similarity or dissimilarity. For example, when comparing the basic information of two companies, the RNN processes their names, industries, addresses, and other attributes, and determines whether the two companies represent the same entity based on the similarity of these attributes. Additionally, it utilizes an attention mechanism to achieve soft alignment of attributes. By calculating the correlation weights between different attributes,

it determines which attributes are more critical in the entity matching process. For example, when comparing two products, price and brand may be more important attributes, while color and size may be relatively less critical. The attention mechanism automatically learns and assigns these weights, allowing the model to focus on the attributes that most significantly impact entity matching.

Ditto (Y. Li, Li, Suhara, Doan, & Tan, 2020) is the latest solution in the field of entity resolution, with its innovation lying in treating the entity resolution task as a sequence pair classification problem and delegating this task to a pre-trained language model. By leveraging the powerful representation capabilities of pre-trained language models, Ditto can more accurately understand the semantic information of entities, thus improving entity resolution performance. Ditto transforms the entity resolution task into a classification problem between two entities.

SkyEx (Isaj, Zimányi, & Pedersen, 2019) proposes a multi-source fusion method for POI matching, which calculates the semantic similarity of POI names using WordNet and analyzes relationships such as synonyms, hypernyms, and hyponyms to determine semantic associations. At the same time, the method combines spatial location information to calculate geographic distances and spatial distribution features to assess the spatial proximity of POIs. SkyEx innovatively introduces multi-source similarity metrics and a Pareto optimal-based matching algorithm, which effectively enhances the accuracy and efficiency of matching. This method does not require hyperparameter tuning and can adapt to different data sources and application needs, providing more precise data support for geographic information systems.

Geo-ER (Balsebre, Yao, Cong, & Hai, 2022) is an innovative method that combines Transformer language models and geographic spatial feature learning. It uses a joint framework to automatically learn the semantic and spatial features of entities, eliminating the reliance on predefined rules. Specifically, the Transformer model captures semantic information from text attributes such as entity names and addresses, while the geographic spatial feature learning framework converts coordinates into spatial embeddings. This bimodal learning approach allows the model to simultaneously understand semantic and spatial contexts, significantly improving the accuracy of geographic entity resolution.

4.4. Entity Resolution Experiment Analysis

The HMN-JFER model proposed in this study adopts the framework shown in Figure 4. A 24-layer BERT model is used as the language model. For spatial information embedding, we conducted comparative experiments using both distance embeddings and GeoHash. Finally, a neighborhood attention module is employed to capture the neighborhood relationships of geographic entities.

The experimental results across four cities in the two datasets are presented in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

The experimental results on the two datasets demonstrate the performance of our HMN-JFER model across different cities (Singapore, Edinburgh, Toronto, and Pittsburgh). As illustrated in the figures, with the increase in training epochs, the accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score of the HMN-JFER model generally show an upward trend. This indicates that the model progressively learns more effective feature representations during training, thereby improving the accuracy of geographic entity matching.

Figure 11. Evaluation metrics on the OSM-FSQ test set

The accuracy metric remains relatively stable with minor fluctuations and consistently maintains a high level, suggesting that HMN-JFER performs well in terms of overall matching accuracy and demonstrates strong stability. The precision metric exhibits some degree of fluctuation across different cities. In the OSM-FSQ dataset for Singapore and Edinburgh, precision shows considerable variation in the early stages but gradually stabilizes as training progresses. This is related to the distribution of positive and negative samples in the dataset and the model’s learning capacity for different categories, which is consistent with the data presented in Table 6. The recall metric fluctuates more significantly in certain cities, particularly in the early stages of training. This is because HMN-JFER initially struggles to identify some hard-to-match entity pairs, resulting in lower recall. As for the F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, its trend reflects the combined changes of the two. In most cases, the F1-score improves with more training epochs, indicating the model’s increasing ability to balance precision and recall. The performance of HMN-JFER also exhibits certain variations across different cities. In the OSM-FSQ Singapore dataset, the model performs relatively stably, with all evaluation metrics maintaining high levels and showing minimal fluctuations. This can be attributed to the higher quality of the Singapore dataset and the more uniform distribution of entities.

(a) OSM-YELP Singapore

(b) OSM-YELP Edinburgh

(c) OSM-YELP Toronto

(d) OSM-YELP Pittsburgh

Figure 12. Evaluation metrics on the OSM-Yelp test set

In the OSM-FSQ Edinburgh dataset, the precision metric experiences significant fluctuations during the early training stages but eventually stabilizes. The recall metric remains relatively steady, indicating that the model is capable of consistently identifying matching entity pairs in Edinburgh.

In contrast, the Toronto and Pittsburgh datasets show greater variability in recall during the initial training stages. This is likely due to the presence of more complex entity matching scenarios in these datasets, such as a higher frequency of entity name similarities that do not correspond to actual matches, as well as larger geographic coordinate discrepancies. These factors contribute to the difficulty of accurate entity recognition in these cities.

The experimental results of the HMN-JFER model on both datasets demonstrate that, as the number of training epochs increases, the model effectively learns the semantic and spatial features of geographic entities, thereby improving matching accuracy. Although certain performance fluctuations are observed across different cities, HMN-JFER generally exhibits strong matching performance and robustness in most cases. These results validate the effectiveness and superiority of the proposed approach in the task of geographic entity resolution, especially in terms of its adaptability to different cities and complex geographic scenarios.

The loss curves for different cities in both datasets are shown in Figure 13. In the experiments conducted on the OSM-FSQ dataset, the loss curves of HMN-JFER illustrate the variation in loss across different cities during the training process. As observed from the figure, the loss values for all cities exhibit a decreasing trend as the number of training epochs increases. This indicates that the model gradually learns more effective feature representations and optimizes its parameters during training, thereby reducing the loss.

Overall, these loss curves reflect the model’s learning dynamics and optimization performance across different city-specific datasets. Although the rate and magnitude of loss reduction vary among cities, the model consistently demonstrates the ability to learn and minimize the loss across all cases, leading to improved matching performance. These results further validate the effectiveness and adaptability of the proposed approach in the task of geographic entity resolution.

Figure 13. Loss curves for cities in both datasets

As shown in Tables 7 and 8, we evaluate the performance of each algorithm on the test datasets using the F1 score as the evaluation metric. For each dataset, the algorithm achieving the highest F1 score is highlighted in bold for easy identification of the best-performing method. Specifically, our proposed method demonstrates a significant performance advantage across all datasets, with improvements in F1 score ranging from at least 1% to as high as 3.5% over the best baseline method GeoER. Based on these experimental results, we conducted a detailed comparative analysis and summarized the following key findings.

First, it is worth noting that algorithms employing pre-trained language models, such as HMN-JFER, Ditto, and GeoER, consistently outperform other algorithms, regardless of whether they are capable of modeling spatial information. This phenomenon suggests that pre-trained language models have a significant advantage in entity resolution tasks. In contrast, DeepMatcher, although utilizing recurrent neural networks and soft alignment mechanisms to compare attributes, fails to effectively model cross-attribute relationships, limiting its performance in complex entity resolution tasks. While SkyEx aims to consider the spatial features of points of interest, it still relies on static string similarity measures and compares attributes independently, which results in poor performance when dealing with entities that have complex spatial relationships. In comparison, the HMN-JFER model, through fine-tuning the pre-trained

language model, can better capture the semantic and spatial features of entities, thus outperforming previous methods in geographic space integration tasks. Additionally, we investigated the comparison between distance embeddings and GeoHash embeddings in geographic space embeddings. The experimental results demonstrate that the GeoHash method outperforms distance embeddings. Even so, HMN-JFER and Geo-ER, which include a distance embedding module, surpass all other models, further proving the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Table 7. F1 Scores of Various Methods in OSM-FSQ

Method	Singapore	Edinburgh	Toronto	Pittsburgh
DeepMatcher	76.6%	88.2%	78.4%	76.9%
SkyEx	72.1%	87.8%	88.0%	85.5%
Ditto	82.6%	92.1%	88.2%	88.7%
Geo-ER	88.5%	93.5%	90.1%	91.8%
HMN-JFER (Distance Embedding)	88.1%	93.1%	90.5%	92.5%
HMN-JFER (GeoHash)	89.5%	94.6%	92.7%	93.7%

Table 8. F1 Scores of Various Methods in OSM-Yelp

Method	Singapore	Edinburgh	Toronto	Pittsburgh
DeepMatcher	80.2%	92.2%	88.5%	90.5%
SkyEx	81.1%	87.6%	91.1%	89.7%
Ditto	86.3%	94.4%	91.5%	93.5%
Geo-ER	87.0%	95.3%	92.7%	95.6%
HMN-JFER (Distance Embedding)	90.3%	95.8%	93.5%	95.5%
HMN-JFER (GeoHash)	92.0%	97.1%	96.2%	97.3%

Additionally, the experimental results reveal an interesting phenomenon: HMN-JFER shows smaller improvements over the baseline algorithms in datasets with more available address information. Specifically, the last column of the table above shows the number of samples where both entities contain non-empty address information. In the Edinburgh dataset, where address information is relatively abundant, the language modeling methods are able to better leverage this information, resulting in improved matching performance. Therefore, the F1 score improvement of our method over the baseline algorithm Ditto is only 2.5% and 2.7% in these datasets. However, in datasets such as Singapore (OSM-FSQ), Toronto (OSM-FSQ), and others, where address information is sparse, the difficulty of entity resolution increases. In these cases, the performance gap between our method and the baseline algorithm Ditto significantly widens, with improvements of 6.9% and 4.5%, respectively. This result further emphasizes the importance of neighborhood attention in HMN-JFER, especially when only partial or incomplete address information is available. These components provide additional contextual information, helping the HMN-JFER model make more accurate entity matches.

4.5. Ablation Study

In order to more comprehensively evaluate the contribution of each component of the HMN-JFER model, we systematically conducted an ablation study. The specific data are shown in Table 9 and Table 10. Specifically, by comparing the original framework with variants where different components were removed, we quantified the impact of each component on the overall performance of the model. The detailed results of the ablation study are reported in Table 5.4. From these results, we observe that the model benefits significantly from the geographic space component, which aligns with the performance analysis reported earlier. Specifically, using only GeoHash embedding leads to a substantial performance improvement. Removing GeoHash in the OSM-FSQ dataset results in performance degradation by 5.2% (Singapore), 2.1% (Edinburgh), 3.2% (Toronto), and 2.4% (Pittsburgh). In the OSM-Yelp dataset, removing GeoHash results in performance degradation by 3.8% (Singapore), 1.4% (Edinburgh), 1.2% (Toronto), and 1.8% (Pittsburgh). This significant drop demonstrates the crucial role of GeoHash embedding in HMN-JFER. As expected, embedding GeoHash separately from the language model enhances the algorithm’s numerical reasoning ability, enabling it to more accurately handle matching tasks involving distances.

Similarly, the heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism also significantly improved performance. In the OSM-FSQ dataset, removing the neighborhood attention leads to performance degradation of 0.9% (Singapore), 0.7% (Edinburgh), 1.2% (Toronto), and 0.4% (Pittsburgh). In the OSM-Yelp dataset, removing the neighborhood attention results in performance degradation of 1.0% (Singapore), 0.9% (Edinburgh), 0.8% (Toronto), and 0.5% (Pittsburgh). This indicates that neighborhood information also plays an important role in enhancing the model’s matching ability. In summary, these two components together have achieved significant performance improvements across all datasets. This result further validates the importance of the geographic space component in the model.

Table 9. Ablation Study on OSM-FSQ Dataset (Evaluation Metric: F1 Score)

Method	Singapore	Edinburgh	Toronto	Pittsburgh
HMN-JFER	89.5%	94.6%	92.7%	93.7%
Remove GeoHash	-5.2%	-2.1%	-3.2%	-2.4%
Remove Neighborhood Attention	-0.9%	-0.7%	-1.2%	-0.4%

Table 10. Ablation Study on OSM-Yelp Dataset (Evaluation Metric: F1 Score)

Method	Singapore	Edinburgh	Toronto	Pittsburgh
HMN-JFER	92.0%	97.1%	96.2%	97.3%
Remove GeoHash	-3.8%	-1.4%	-1.2%	-1.8%
Remove Neighborhood Attention	-1.0%	-0.9%	-0.8%	-0.5%

4.6. Neighborhood Attention in Sparse and Dense Scenarios

For the geographic entities to be matched, we define the following scenarios: When the distance between the entity pairs is less than 100 meters and the number of points of interest in the neighborhood exceeds 10, the entity pair is considered to be in a dense scenario. Conversely, when the distance between the entity pairs exceeds 1000 meters and the number of points of interest in their neighborhood is less than or equal to 2, the entity pair is considered to be in a sparse scenario. Based on these definitions, we obtained all the entity pairs in both sparse and dense scenarios from the Toronto dataset in the OSM-FSQ. Specifically, there are 737 entity pairs in dense scenarios and 303 entity pairs in sparse scenarios. In the following, we experimentally verify the F1 score improvement of neighborhood attention in these two special scenarios.

In the OSM-FSQ Toronto dataset, the F1 score improvement of the heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism shows significant differences between the dense and sparse scenarios. In the dense scenario, there are a total of 737 entity pairs, with a baseline F1 score of 79.1%. The heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism improves this by 9.1%, resulting in a final F1 score of 88.2%. The key reasons for this significant improvement include the richness of neighborhood information, the modeling ability for complex spatial relationships, and noise suppression. In dense areas, there are many points of interest (POIs), and neighborhood attention dynamically aggregates semantic and spatial features from multiple neighboring entities (such as name similarity and category consistency), effectively distinguishing between entities with the same name but independent existence, such as chain stores in busy commercial areas. For entity pairs that are close in distance (≤ 100 meters), localization errors can easily lead to misjudgment. Neighborhood attention mitigates the impact of small errors through a distance bias term and adjusts weights based on neighborhood density, for instance, by reducing the probability of matching same-name entities in high-density areas. Additionally, in dense areas, data noise (such as duplicate POIs) is more prevalent, and neighborhood attention improves the model’s robustness by integrating multi-source features, including text, spatial, and contextual information.

Table 11. Performance Comparison of Heterogeneous Neighborhood Attention Mechanism in Different Scenarios (Evaluation Metric: F1 Score)

Method	Dense Scenario	Sparse Scenario
Without Neighborhood Attention	79.1%	80.2%
With Neighborhood Attention	+9.1%	+2.9%

In the sparse scenario, there are a total of 303 entity pairs, with a baseline F1 score of 82.2%. The neighborhood attention mechanism improves this by 3.9%, resulting in a final F1 score of 86.1%. The key reasons for this improvement lie in the limited neighborhood information, the enhanced long-distance entity correlation, and the supplementation of heterogeneous attributes. In sparse areas, there are fewer points of interest (< 2), and neighborhood attention mitigates the impact of single localization bias by expanding the neighborhood radius (e.g., set to 500 meters in suburban areas) to cover potential matching entities. When entity pairs are located farther apart (> 1000 meters), traditional methods may misjudge due to isolated features, while neighborhood attention enhances discriminative evidence by utilizing semantic similarity (such as address keywords) and sparse neighborhood distribution features (such

as uniqueness). Additionally, when text attributes (such as address descriptions) are missing or heterogeneous, neighborhood context (such as nearby road names) provides supplementary information.

The difference in performance improvement between dense and sparse scenarios highlights the critical role of neighborhood information in complex environments. In terms of optimization, for dense scenarios, a dynamic neighborhood radius can be introduced to adjust the attention weights based on entity types. For sparse scenarios, global context such as regional functional distribution can be integrated to compensate for the lack of local neighborhood information. In practical applications, this mechanism is suitable for scenarios that require high-precision matching, such as urban navigation and logistics distribution, especially when data heterogeneity and noise coexist. In summary, the neighborhood attention mechanism significantly improves matching accuracy in dense scenarios through context awareness and dynamic weight allocation, while also demonstrating robustness in sparse scenarios, offering an adaptive solution for geographic entity resolution.

5. Conclusion

Traditional entity resolution techniques are primarily designed for structured data and often overlook the differences between attributes and their varying contributions to the final matching decision. These methods lack the ability to adaptively select appropriate similarity metrics for different attributes, resulting in limited generalization capabilities. Moreover, they face significant challenges when dealing with unstructured data. Although deep learning has been introduced to address these issues, existing deep learning-based approaches still have limitations, such as insufficient extraction of record information, high dependence on labeled data, and the need for expert knowledge injection. To overcome these challenges, this paper proposes the following key contributions:

- (1) **GeoHash Encoding Method:** To address the challenge of processing latitude and longitude data in geographic entity resolution, this paper introduces the GeoHash encoding method. GeoHash converts geographic coordinates into strings, simplifying the processing and storage of spatial data. With its spatial hierarchy, GeoHash allows for flexible adjustment of encoding length based on practical needs, thus ensuring matching accuracy while optimizing computational resources. Experimental results demonstrate that GeoHash outperforms traditional distance embeddings across all datasets.
- (2) **Heterogeneous Neighborhood Attention Mechanism:** To tackle the challenges posed by complex scenarios in geographic entity resolution, this paper proposes a heterogeneous neighborhood attention mechanism. This mechanism dynamically aggregates the semantic and spatial relationships between central entities and their neighboring entities to construct context-aware representations, enhancing the model’s adaptability to diverse geographic environments. By integrating graph attention networks with spatial distance bias, the mechanism simultaneously captures name semantic similarity and spatial proximity, avoiding bias from any single dimension. Experiments show that this mechanism significantly improves matching accuracy in dense scenarios and demonstrates robustness in sparse environments.

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